

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

IMPORTANT WAYS OF CREATING DAILY HABITS FOR NEW LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. *This given article provides some practical tips for developing daily habits to learn one language effectively. Also it can carry some specific details and ways how to overcome given steps with a clear motivation.*

Key words: *Language learning process, vocabulary range, repetition, goal setting, smart planning, daily podcasts, various stories.*

Learning new language can seem as daunting work especially its beginning, as it like a brain multitasking or loading too much pressure on someone's shoulder. Because, in language learning, we often find ourselves under the pressure and overthink too much; how to learn a language quickly and with less effort. However, it is absolutely depending on the right mind set and necessary tools. Moreover, there's reliable truth that learning another language may take both time and energy, also hard work. Nobody heard about the one who learned to speak one language like a native in one day, neither did I. That's because, myths like that doesn't exist. There are a lot of reasons to learn a second or third language, and too many ways to make it into practice, but there is a proper question which everyone interests is that, what is the best and easiest way of it? This article will show some reasons till the end.

How to learn a new language?

People who starts to learn unfamiliar language should know, language learning is a bit tougher step which anyone can feel its starting but it is not a simple task that finishes in a quick mode. Even there is no one exact, right method for learning a new language, this multitasking depends on everyone's taste, they choose to be in some different ways. These may include video and audio segments, games, language learning apps, the continuousness of the practice, consuming media factors, conversations in another language. As *John Gallagher* emphasized that “*the first thing to do when learning a language is to forget about fluency (whatever that means). Setting achievable, measurable goals is crucial to successful language learning.*” These concepts show truly that if anyone who wants to open up his/her ability in one sphere must be ready to overcome the obstacles. Right at the beginning of the journey, it might be with learning new alphabets or learning some basic phrases which are needed.

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Deciding on goals: This also is a crucial part of learning. Individuals waste their time to think over and over again which language to learn, but necessary thing is to spend the attention *how* of language learning.

1. Set a specific goal, setting as specific as possible learner must know what and when to achieve.
2. Relevant, which means the setting goals must suit relevant and specific with the learners' ambitions.
3. Set the time, using *deadline* is crucial way of setting and finishing the goal.

Creating a plan: Another important step of creating new language habits is creating a systematic plan righteously. Language study plans are the parts of effective language learning. Being a perfect planner, the learner should spend at least 15-20 minutes a day without doing any tasks. These can lead them to accomplish their acquisition goal. Head of Methodology at Preply, the expert in this field of language learning process, *Sylvia* comments: *“Language study plans are the key to effective language learning. By having study plan, learners feel accountable for completing their tasks. Time is precious commodity these days, and focused students see this time as an investment.”*

Escape from being bored: Make every part of learning fun, repetitions mustn't be boring. Doing every given task with joy, and doing the things most enjoyable can give more energy to emphasise or clarify new tasks. Approaching the language learning journey in a positive mood is fundamental. Learners should try to estimate themselves with a huge grade, even delight in achieving small goals they set. Especially, should never forget to take an experience just a little tasks.

Listening audios: Another helpful hint of learning is listening to the range of podcasts, audios which are proven to improve both speaking and listening (BBC Sound Podcasts, Google Podcasts, Apple Podcasts) Also it can share learner the taste of being freedom in learning and be at your own pace.

Watching TV: Every single learner can watch films, clips with subtitles on TV, helps to enhance the comprehension.

Keeping a language diary: Keeping various types of diaries provide many benefits for language learning. For example: recording and revising necessary words, word structures, reviewing old concepts, checking the progress.

Revision: Another useful factor is to revise learning. Revising what the learner understood is the most successful technique for boosting the pace of language learning

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process. Daily repetition will encourage them to have vocabulary, grammar rules faster in mind.

Using from sticky notes: This instruction is also famous among the learners. First they stick notes onto places which are relevant and other places that they constantly look at or walk through. Like onto furniture, mirrors, walls, kitchen cabins so that can repeatedly remind the words which they may face a challenge to remember or the words that are forgotten.

Change irrelevant habits: Learners must take a look at the things they do on a daily basis change them if they are not reliable or irrelevant.

These given instructions below are the researches which I examined with the learners, can help you not to overcome heavy challenges at all. The most proper concepts were given to the learners as making notes after every lesson gives to be in progress fast. Or working with an expert or tutor can lead them to work individually. Furthermore, anyone who wants to be like an expert should calculate every single movement. If they use the tips and hints provided in this article, can fight the laziness and dreaded forgetting by staying motivated and being persistent.

CONCLUSION: Language learning requires much time also responsibility that commits doing every day. These may seem a bit struggling but those daily practices I showed can lead you on a journey of big achievements, which brings you to the ultimate goal. In conclusion language learning, creating specific habits are a marathon, not an easy journey. The process takes continuously practice, the help from other partners, various breakdowns. Nevertheless, this journey's practice depends on the learners' themselves; their creativity, hard work, personalized plan, specific goals and etc. Best luck to every language learner.

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